

EDUCATIONAL SERVICES OF THE EU COUNTRIES FOR FOREIGNERS IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract: *The European Union, which is known as one of the largest organizations and comprises 27 countries, has developed over the years several mechanisms that brought the citizens closer and promoted common educational language connecting all the citizens and leads the continent economy and education - the educational system. Over 23 years ago higher education has already knew to establish applicable idea of common academic space, with standards that are uniform on one hand, but on the other hand, also acknowledges uniform academic culture and language. These processes have created competition between the academia institutes and promoted the research and technology of institutes that are interested to meet the competition. This article will try to review the activity of the union counties and how to attract higher education students from other countries.*

Key Words: *European Union; Educational Services; International Students.*

SERVICII EDUCAȚIONALE ALE ȚĂRILOR UE PENTRU STRĂINI ÎN CONDIȚII MODERNE

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Rezumat: *Uniunea Europeană, care este cunoscută ca una dintre cele mai mari organizații și cuprinde 27 de țări, a dezvoltat de-a lungul anilor mai multe mecanisme care au apropiat cetățenii și au promovat un limbaj educațional comun care leagă toți cetățenii și conduce economia și educația continentului - sistem educațional. Cu peste 23 de ani în urmă, învățământul superior știa deja să stabilească ideea aplicabilă a spațiului academic comun, cu standarde care sunt uniforme pe de o parte, dar, pe de altă parte, recunoaște și*

cultura și limba academică uniforme. Aceste procese au creat competiție între institutele academice și au promovat cercetarea și tehnologia institutelor care sunt interesate să îndeplinească competiția. Acest articol va încerca să treacă în revistă activitatea județelor unite și modul de atragere a studenților din învățământul superior din alte țări.

Cuvinte cheie: Uniunea Europeană; servicii educaționale; studenți internaționali.

1. Introduction

The European Union has gone a long way from the time it was a union of limited economic cooperation between countries until its present shape. The number of countries that joined the mutual agreements of the European community have increased and it became the European Union, and, as mentioned, comprises 27 countries. This extension required increasing cooperation in economy, society and politics and forming mutual policy in many fields. Since 1992 there is a common European market, which allows free pass of merchandise and people and, in fact, abolishes national borders that became symbolic. Applying the union currency, the Euro, in 2002 in 12 countries has strengthened this trend. The European Union promotes cooperation between citizens from the member countries in education and society to overcome culture and language differences. Until its recent extension in May 2004, there were 382 million people in the European Union. As for 2020, there are 445 million people, and if considering the union as one demographic unit, it is the third largest area in the world, after China and India.

2. Main Materials

The European Union and higher education. According to Teichler [11], the process that unify the education discipline has begun in the **Bologna Process (1999)**. The Bologna Process is a convention enshrined by the European Union which discusses comprehensive standardization between universities in European countries and aimed to provide mutual recognition of curricula and academic degrees. De wit [5] notes that the process was gradual and planned to be completed in 2010. This process, according to De wit [4], deals with standardization and adjustment of courses and academic credit points for identical degrees all over the continent. He says it requires **immediate and simple recognition** of academic study value in neighboring European countries, despite differences of language, culture, and place. This understanding is important because before the Bologna Process each case was discussed individually. Unifying the academic process in Europe is a process that allows the European market to assess and employ academic employees from other countries as well as rely on academic products, as

scientific and social research, and it is an additional and significant process and makes Europe the multinational federation called the European Union.

One of the academic mobility processes that has extended is internationalization in the higher education system. **Internationalization in the higher education system** refers to the process integrating the international, intercultural, and global aspects in the organization goals, in its functioning and its activities. By the definition of Knight [9], internationalization is a process that occurs all over the organization and may happen in any of its activity aspects. Therefore, internationalization and globalization are related. Knight [8] says that internationalization changes the higher education world and globalization changes the internationalization world. In other words, globalization changes the education system while one of the significant changes is making the international dimension more central in the discussion of heads of institutions and policy makers in education, especially since it is an index of the academic institute quality and the quality of the education system in the country.

The European Union plans for integration of foreign students. According to the European Union decisions, the member countries are responsible for education and the European Union institutes have only a supportive role [3]. According to decision 165 of the convention for European Union functioning, the European community will contribute to developing quality education by encouraging cooperation between the member countries through activities as promoting citizen mobility, planning mutual curricula, establishing networks, information exchange or teaching the European Union languages. In addition, as notes Altbach & De wit [1], the European Union also funds education programs, professionalism and building citizenship that encourages the European Union citizens to use the opportunity it offers them **to live, study and work in other countries**. The best known is the ERASMUS program, in which more than 3,000,000 students took part in interim and university exchanges during the last 20 years (since 2000). Since the European Union countries were aware of the importance of education and training to their economic and social goals, they began working together since 2000 to achieve specific goals in education [10]. Academic cooperation began by sharing examples of good policy managers, participation in peer learning activities, setting standards and following the progress with main indicators. **Currently, the 27 member countries strive to respond coherently to shared challenges, while maintaining their sovereignty in education policy.** This strategy called the 2020 education and training program (ET2020), which is an update of the 2010 education and training program. The European Union is also part of various inter-governmental projects, including the Bologna Process that

planned to make a European higher education area by harmonization of academic degree structure and standards and academic quality assurance standards in all the European Union countries and in other countries in Europe. Therefore, countries will not hesitate to invest the required resources to attract foreign students [12].

Allocating resources for foreign student mobility. The competition between countries and between tertiary education institutes currently works in many activity channels that helps them attract foreign students to the country and the academic institute. Many countries, including European Union countries, operate for many years **national mechanisms that are aimed to viabilities international students entering the country, and the institutions.** The article editor indicates the German organization DAAT, which leads and manages the interrogation and escorting system for foreign student arriving to study in Germany. There are also parallel organizations in the USA, Australia, Finland, Spain and additional countries. Such organizations run a structured quality control system in academic institutes, budget issues for foreign student integration, up to funding financial scholarships to ease the foreign student integration in the integrating country and institute.

Thondhlana et al [12] even notes that in most cases it is economic - occupational interest that aims to enrich the academic institution coffers (the foreign student tuition is higher than the local), and in many cases they also try to make the student stay in the integrating country and in the local occupational market. Additional resources the tertiary education institutes invest in the European Union are for teaching quality processes. Among this resource allocation there are investments in teaching teams and workforce standards.

Resource allocation for improving teaching quality and ensuring workforce quality. In the European Union conference in 2015 it was decided to adopt the proposed model for improving teaching quality in higher education institutes, by which all higher education institutes will be obligated to apply several basic mechanisms to improve teaching quality. According to the European council decision, each higher education institute will have mechanism that will be responsible for: (1) teaching training for each new staff member in all levels, including external teachers and teaching assistants. (2) having regular teaching evaluation questionnaires every semester and in all the institution courses in the student language (local/foreign student). Lecturers that their teaching review results are exceptionally good, will be praised / rewarded. On the other hand, institutes will be able to act against lecturers that have low teaching review results. In addition, there will be an open and public debate about publication and distribution of detailed syllabus for all courses as well as the course requirements and the grade

calculation method. Therefore, the European council has decided to allocate a special budget to academic institutes that integrate foreign students.

Allocating budgetary resources for the STEAM (science, technology, engineering, the arts, and mathematics) subjects. The European council supports since 2017 the call to train today's learners for tomorrow's world. Brandenburg et al [2] notes it is especially important regarding interdisciplinary learning and especially paying attention to integration between science, technology, engineering, arts and mathematics (STEAM). This trend raises questions about the pedagogy of interdisciplinary education to STEM in the aspects of teaching, learning and evaluation in all tertiary education frameworks, as well as questions concerning realizing the idea and vision in the education system and research institutes. The council agrees it has long term effects on the learners. As for today, although there is no unity in STEAM interdisciplinary learning and teaching approaches, there is an agreement regarding its advantages for the learner and its adequacy to 21st century skills. These advantages includes deepening understanding of STEAM disciplines: (a) developing entrepreneurial spirit, curiosity, creativity and mental flexibility; (b) promoting independent learner skills and decision making, and developing awareness to aesthetics and moral; (c) developing research skills and ability to solve problems in diverse methods; (d) nurturing social skills and interpersonal communication, including developing ability to cooperative teamwork and openness to multiple perspectives.

Allocating resources for implementing digital technologies in higher education systems. Additional subject the European Union tertiary education deals with is the problems and obstacles in assimilating digital technologies in higher education systems. Within the process the education committee of the European council coped with the paradox of many issues: (1) the differential infrastructure and higher education institutes willing to use the potential in technologies; (2) how much do "old" distance education technologies and new technologies replace the teaching / learning methods in class; (3) the real functioning, problems, barriers and obstacles in implementing new technologies; (4) new technology influence on student customers; (5) acquiring information versus building knowledge in higher education; (6) cost consideration; (7) the human ability to adjust to new learning styles due to technology fast development; and (8) the organizational cultures of the academic and organizational world.

Allocating resources for vocational training to European Union citizens. The European Union, as part of continental strategy, seeks to encourage the member countries to improve the quality and relevance of higher education and vocational education and training (VET) by constant follow up of graduates as part

of the European follow up initiation in training programs and vocational education. Craciun [3] adds that allocating this resource aimed to assess whether the graduate knowledge and skills are qualitative and relevant enough to allow them to succeed in the current and the future labor world. These efforts made by the Union since 2018 allow to improve data comparison of current population with the graduate results at European level and thus contribute to the realization of a real modern and professional European education until 2030.

The Union strategic line will provide “key insights” for policy makers and allow them to cope with education challenges and trans-national skills while using an approach based on real data of employment needs and demand for various professionals and positions.

In addition, monitoring European Union education program graduates helps in:

- Improving the experience of international students (foreign in the integrating country) and system graduates and identifying opportunities to improve teaching and learning effectiveness to integrate them later in the occupation market (Finland, Germany, Norway, Portugal).

- Strengthen the occupation ability of the graduates (local and foreign) by improving skill planning and adjusting it to employer needs, designing curricula and career guidance and integration in the new country.

- Having insights about border crossing mobility patterns, including excessive education cases (like in Israel), and on the other hand, populations who lack skills.

- Focus the investment on quality education adjusted to international student needs, but on the other hand local students also benefit from high standardization.

3. Conclusions

Basing on the findings, the article editor concludes several conclusions brought later:

1. Continue the dialog between the states and the Union and create additional harmonization process of monitoring international students by establishing national expert network in each country to direct the national efforts to follow the graduates and ease their connection with European colleagues.

2. Establish national mechanisms to unify the method of treating foreign student arriving to higher education and allow him to work in his qualification field after graduation.

3. In 2025, the European commission will examine the progress achieved in implementing the council recommendation and expects to see 80% integration among member countries until the end of 2024.

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